

A STUDY ON STRESS MANAGEMENT OF EMPLOYEE ON SRI VINAYAGA CONTAINERS SIPCOT, INDUSTRIAL COMPLEX, DINDIGUL

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Abstract:

Stress is the emotional and physical strain caused by our response to pressure from outside the world. It is a dynamic condition in which an individual is confronted with an opportunity, constraint, or demand related to what he or she desires and for which the outcome is perceived to be both uncertain and unimportant. Stress is also often typified by a lack of control over conditions at work. Stress is the physical and mental response of the body to demands made upon it. It is the result of our reaction to outside events, not necessarily the events themselves. Stress is the anticipated and unavoidable element of life due to unavoidable element of life due to ever increasing complexities and competitiveness in living standards. The speed of change in humankind today is certainly overwhelming and breathtaking. In the fast changing world of today, no individuals are free from stress nor is any profession stress free. It is just not enough to treat the causes but the consequences of stress on physical, emotion and behaviors areas also require due attention.

Key Words: Types of Stress, Signs of Stress, Physical & Mental Response.

Introduction:

Stress is a normal physical response to events that makes one feel upset in some way or the other. In today's modern world, life is so full of hassles, deadlines and demand that stress has become a mode of life. People usually think of stress as a negative experience. According biological point of view, stress can be a neutral, negative or positive experience. It is not always bad and it can help individuals to perform well under pressure. But a person constantly running in the emergency mode is sure to harm one's mind and body. It is thus essential to balance and manage stress in positive way to lead a healthy life in body, mind and spirit.

Some Types of Stress:

Physical Stress:

- Time Stress
- Anticipatory Stress
- Situational Stress
- Encounter Stress

Emotional Stress:

- Anxiety or Irritability
- Depression
- Panic Attacks
- Sadness

Acute Stress:

- Traffic jams
- Crowds
- Loud noises
- Running late
- Impending deadlines for work related projects

Emotional Stress:

- Anxiety
- Anger
- Irritability: short temper
- Impatience

Chronic Stress:

- Upset Stomach
- Headaches
- Using Drugs
- Decreased Energy
- Heart Disease
- Memory Problems

Statement of the Problem:

Modern living has brought with it, not only immeasurable means of comfort, but also an overabundance of demand that tax human body and mind. Nowadays, everyone talks about stress. It is prevalent across all socioeconomic group of population. Not only just high pressure executives are its key victims but it also includes laborers, slum dwellers, working women, businessmen, professionals and even children. Stress is the anticipated and unavoidable element of life due to unavoidable element of life due to ever increasing complexities and competitiveness in living standards. The speed of change in humankind today is certainly overwhelming and breathtaking. In the fast changing world of today, no individuals is free from stress nor is any profession stress free.

Objectives of the Study:

- To identify the major sources of stress of employees in the company.
- To assess the level of stress experienced by the workers.
- To identify the situations that cause stress among workers.
- To understand satisfaction level and physical & mental strain of workers.

Scope of the Study:

- The organization have now realized the importance of stress management however, they focus on the reduction or management of the job related stressors alone, but the impact of personal stressors like family and social commitments do have a bearing on the emotional stability and physical ability of the employee.
- It is just not enough to treat the causes but the consequences of stress one physical, emotion and behaviors areas also require due attention.
- In this way, this study could be extended so as to include the personal stresses and the consequences of the stress may those be identified so as to enable the employee is the better management of their response to stressors.
- Considering the role of worker the data can be obtained at different stages of the schedule of work and the variations in the stress level can also be studied

Research Methodology:

Research in common parlance refers to search of knowledge. Business research can be defined the systematic enquiry whose objective is to provide information to solve managerial problem.

Research Design:

- It is the arrangement of conditions for collection and analysis of data in a manual that aims to combine relative to the research purpose with economy in procedure.
- The research design is the conception stature for the collection, measurement and analysis. The nature of study is a descriptive research. It studies those, which are concerned with describing the characteristics of a particular individual or of a group.

Sampling Design:

The sample design that has been under taken is convenient sampling.

Methods of Data Collection:

The task of data collection begins after a research problem has been and research design or plan chalked out.

Primary Data:

Primary data are those, which are collection afresh and for the first and thus happen to be original in character. The primary data is collected through questionnaire method. In this method, questionnaire is sent to the presence concern with request to answer the question and return the questionnaire. A questionnaire consists of number of questions printed or typed in a definite order on a form or set of forms.

Secondary Data:

Secondary data means, data that already available. They refer to the data is have already been collected and analyzed by someone else. Secondary may either be published data or unpublished data usually data available in technical and trade journals, reports and publication of various association connect with business and industry, letter, research work

Tools Used for Research:

- Simple Percentage Method
- Chi - Square Test
- Correlation

Review of Literature:

Kushnir, Talma; Melamed, and samuel in their study titled "Domestic stress and well- being of Employed Women" 54 (9):687-694 "Interplay between demands and decision control at work" (2008). Respondents were 133 mothers employed in secretarial and managerial jobs. It is suggested that in families (as in Teams), shared decision control may be more potent copying resources than person.

Keeva , and Stevan in their article titled "Depression Takes a Toll 92: 37-38 "American Bar Association Journal" (2008) deal with the high rates of mental depression among lawyers in the in the U.S studies which highlighted the depression problem among lawyers are cited. It discusses the suicide of judge Mack kidd of Austin, Texas. It explores the role of occupational stress in depression among lawyers.

Glanville, Julie. In their research articles "The prevalence of nursing staff stress on adult acute psychiatric in-patient wards" 41 (1):34 - 43 "Social psychiatry and psychiatric epidemiology"(2009) their study reviewed the prevalence of low staff morale, due to stress, burnout, job satisfaction and psychological well being amongst staff working in in-patient psychiatric wards.

H. Azlihanis A; L. Naing; D. Aziah; N. Rusli in their titled "Socio-demographic, Occupational and

psychological factors Associated with job strain among secondary school teachers in kota Bhsru, kelantan” 40 (6):1359-70”South Asian J Trop Med Public Health”(2010) they conducted a study to identify the factors associated with job strain among teachers working in secondary schools kota Bharu , kelatan. A Sample size of 580 teachers was taken. The result was significant. There was linear relationship between job strain and the duration of service in the present employment, duration of working hours, job insecurity and the social support.

Suggestions:

- It is very difficult to work in continuous shift. The company can avoid such situation.
- The company can try to increase the employee earnings and improve their present working conditions.
- The workload of the employees can be reduced by the company for reducing the stress of employee.
- Company should provide the feedback for the employee’s performance. It helps in reducing the stress level of employees.
- Management should provide adequate infrastructure facility. It will help in reducing the stress of employees.

Conclusion:

Discuss stress and its management are should understand that this is not the exhaustive list of the stress factors and various techniques. Stress can be confronted and reduced if and only. If we understand ourselves better, analyze the behavior and identify the stressors. The stress management techniques will work if we are honest with ourselves and adopt the techniques in their fullest spirit. The project was carried out in SRI Vinayaga Containers Pvt. Ltd. It was an attempt to study the roles stress among employees in the company and to evaluate the overall satisfaction level of employees towards the stress provided in the company. The descriptive research design, chi-square and correlation test are used. From this data analysis, I have given few suggestion regarding the role of stress, more improvement in the company is supportive (physically, emotionally and (financially) in case of illness, accident, bereavement etc.

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